

Simplemux traffic optimization protocol

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a user-space C implementation of Simplemux, an experimental network protocol designed to improve efficiency and reliability in packet-switched networks. It provides two main functionalities: (i) traffic saving, by aggregating small packets into larger ones to reduce bandwidth consumption and packets per second; and (ii) fast delivery grant, by redundantly sending critical packets to minimize latency over unreliable links. The implementation includes three flavors (compressed, fast, blast), multiple transport modes, Robust Header Compression, and configurable multiplexing policies. Simplemux has been applied in research on online gaming, VoIP optimization, and smart grid communications.

Metadata

Nr	Code metadata description	Metadata
C1	Current code version	v4.1
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/Simplemux/simplemux , https://gitlab.com/josemariasaldana/simplemux/-/tags/v4.1 and https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17209552
C3	Permanent link to reproducible capsule	N/A
C4	Legal code license	GNU General Public License (GPL) version 3.
C5	Code versioning system used	Git
C6	Software code languages, tools and services used	C, Perl, Markdown, LUA.
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments and dependencies	Linux standard libraries
C8	If available, link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/Simplemux/simplemux/blob/master/README.md , https://gitlab.com/josemariasaldana/simplemux/-/blob/master/README.md
C9	Support email for questions	jmsaldana@fcirce.es

1. Motivation and significance

1.1. Background and relevance

This paper presents a user-space C implementation of Simplemux, an experimental network protocol designed to address two problems: network inefficiency, and delivery uncertainty. To that end, it includes two main functionalities: (a) *traffic saving*: to modify the profile of network traffic by grouping small packets into larger ones; (b) *fast delivery grant*: to grant the fast delivery of certain packets carrying critical information between locations connected by unreliable networks.

The *traffic saving* functionality is aimed at addressing the low network efficiency caused by the prevalence of small packets in modern networks. In many cases, the headers and payloads of these packets can be similarly large, often of comparable magnitude. In some cases, multiplexing (i.e., aggregating) a number of small packets into a larger one can improve efficiency. As illustrated in Fig. 1, several small packets can be aggregated and sent together between two machines if they share a common network path. This may occur between machines in different locations, or within a datacenter, in which virtual machines used by the same organization are hosted on different servers. By shifting the traffic profile from small packets to larger ones, network overhead is reduced, and so is the number of packets per second generated: this can reduce the number of packets to be managed by switches, routers or other intermediate network devices.

The *fast delivery grant* functionality is useful when small packets carry information corresponding to services with critical latency constraints, along with delivery guarantees. In these cases, redundantly sending the

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same packet a number of times can be a way to grant a fast delivery. As an example, this may be useful for sending event-driven commands between remote facilities connected by unreliable networks. In this case, application-level ACKs are employed: packets are sent periodically until they are acknowledged by the other side.

Simplemux has three *flavors*: the *compressed* one is designed for the *traffic saving* functionality, i.e., it is capable of encapsulating multiple packets from different protocols into a single bundle. The *fast* flavor is a simplified version of the *compressed* one, which sacrifices some overhead reduction, in exchange for a simpler implementation. Finally, the *blast* flavor implements the *fast delivery grant* functionality. In the three flavors, small headers (separators) are added at the beginning of each multiplexed packet.

As far as the separators are concerned, in the *compressed* flavor the separators include two flags: one expressing whether all the encapsulated packets belong to the same protocol (Single-Protocol Bit, SPB, which only appears in the first separator), and another one to express if the length of the packet requires one or two bytes (Length Extension, LXT). The headers of *fast* and *blast* flavors are of fixed size. In the *blast* flavor, headers also include an identifier, since verification of each packet's arrival is required at the other side. Application-level ACKs simply consist of a header without any payload.

The separators include a *Protocol* field, corresponding to the IANA "Assigned Internet Protocol Numbers" [1], which defines the identifier used for each protocol. It allows the aggregation of packets from virtually any protocol (the "multiplexed packets") into a single packet belonging to another (or the same) protocol (the "tunnelling protocol"). To minimize the overhead, in the *compressed* flavor, the size of the multiplexing headers is kept very small, potentially a single byte when multiplexing small packets; furthermore, the size of the native headers can be significantly reduced by using standard compression mechanisms [2] based on avoiding fields which value is constant, or that can be reduced because of its incremental behavior.

The implementation includes three tunneling protocols, resulting in the corresponding *modes*: (a) in *network* mode, packets or frames are sent over IPv4, using raw sockets (with Protocol Number 253 or 254, defined by IANA as "Use for experimentation and testing" [1]); (b) UDP and (c) TCP (in these cases, the port can be defined by the user).

Regarding the tunneled protocols, the implementation can send Ethernet frames (*tap* tunneling mode). The protocol stack for network mode, UDP and TCP modes is presented in Fig. 2(a) or IP packets (for the three options using *tun* tunneling mode see Fig. 2(b)).

1.2. Usage of Simplemux in research studies

a) Real-Time Media Traffic

Before the development of the current implementation, some research papers used simulations or theoretical calculations to explore the trade-off between the potential savings (in terms of bandwidth and packets-per-second) and the added delay. In [3], real traffic traces of eight First Person Shooter online games were optimized, showing that playability could be kept within acceptable limits while reducing the throughput. Other papers studied the influence on Voice over IP (VoIP) [4], Massive Multiplayer Online

Role-Playing Games (MMORPG) [5], and other use cases [6], always using real captures. A similar approach was followed in [7] for cloud games. All these services generate small packets with high frequency, which makes them quite suitable for compression.

Previous versions of Simplemux were used in different research papers: regarding the *traffic saving* functionality, it was used in [8] to improve the traffic profile of a TCP-based MMORPG, showing its benefits in terms of bandwidth and packet-per-second savings, while maintaining playability. In [9] it was used for the optimization of VoIP traffic (using RTP over UDP), showing a 46 % bandwidth saving; a public traffic trace with many different flows was also optimized, reducing the packets per second by 50 %; finally, reduction of airtime usage was achieved in an 802.11 deployment.

b) Industrial Control Traffic

The *fast delivery grant* functionality was tested in [10], for improving the reliability of a Wide Area Monitoring Protection and Control (WAMPAC) electric system including several remote substations [11], some of which were connected through unreliable networks. Event-driven commands for the inter-area protection of electric systems were sent with the Simplemux *blast* flavor, improving the packet delivery rate and the stability of the electric network.

1.3. Related work in the literature: algorithms used

Simplemux combines three features: tunneling, multiplexing and header compression. Many tunneling options exist (non-exhaustive list) such as GRE [12], able to encapsulate a wide variety of network layer protocols; L2TP, which provides no encryption by itself and is usually paired with IPsec for security [13]; or more recently Geneve [14], a tunneling method for network virtualization [15]. Regarding multiplexing, QUIC [16] works at Transport layer, and it can multiplex several streams over a single UDP connection. At higher layers, HTTP/2 multiplexes several HTTP requests/responses over a single TCP connection.

The work presented in [17] uses VoIP to compare several tunneling and security protocols, including GRE with IPsec (GRE+IPsec), IP-in-IP with SIP-based signaling (IPIP+SIP), Secure Sockets Layer (SSL), and L2TP with IPsec (L2TP+IPsec). Another comparison, mainly centered on VPNs, can be found in [18].

Robust Header Compression [2] is the most widely used protocol for reducing the size of the IP, TCP, UDP and also RTP headers: as the multiplexed packet travels through a tunnel, some information of the header can be removed between the two endpoints. RoHC implements two mechanisms: first, the fields of the header that are always the same (e.g. IP addresses, ports) can be avoided; second, other fields with an incremental behavior (e.g. TCP windows, sequence numbers) can be encoded with less bytes. To make this possible, a set of variables (called "the context") is stored on both sides, and a feedback channel is required to keep them synchronized. A publicly available RoHC library has been used [19].

2. Software description

The software has been enhanced with two new functionalities,

Fig. 1. Traffic saving functionality: Optimization of traffic between two machines in different locations.

Fig. 2. UDP/IP packet sent in a) tap tunneling mode; b) tun tunneling mode: network, UDP and TCP modes.

namely *fast* and *blast* flavors, compared to the versions used in previous research. Additionally, the code has been refactored and organized to improve readability and maintainability. Updated documentation has been added to the repository, along with Wireshark dissectors and capture examples.

2.1. Software architecture

The architecture of the application, including the main elements and their interconnections, is shown in Fig. 3. As already explained, Simplemux connects two different networks, so it uses a network interface connected to the local network, and another one to the remote end. The

Fig. 3. Software architecture of the presented Simplemux implementation.

application runs in both communication ends: on each side, the IP address of the other end is defined, thus allowing the creation of a tunnel.

The application manages three network sockets. It has the classic structure corresponding to a network protocol implementation: an infinite loop including a ‘poll’ command. Therefore, actions are taken whenever a new packet or frame arrives at one of the sockets, or a period expires.

Native frames or packets are captured in the local machine using the *local* socket, connected to a *tap* or *tun* interface, respectively. Different mechanisms can be used to redirect certain local frames or packets to these interfaces: an internal bridge, routing with *iptables*, etc.

In *tap* mode, Ethernet frames are captured, and this allows the creation of a Layer-2 tunnel between two networks. As an example, in [10], Ethernet frames of the IEC 61850 GOOSE protocol were exchanged between remote locations. This protocol is used for the management of electric substations. In *tun* mode, Simplemux works at IP level, i.e., it captures, aggregates and sends IP packets. In this mode, header compression can be employed to reduce the size of the tunneled IP, TCP, UDP or RTP headers.

In *compressed* and *fast* flavors, the captured native packets or frames are stored in a buffer, which is managed by the *tun/tap to network* module. The buffer is emptied according to different multiplexing policies, i.e., the criteria for deciding which packets are grouped together and forwarded to the remote machine via the *remote* socket.

There are four multiplexing policies: (a) *number*: to wait until a number of packets has arrived; (b) *period*: to wait until a period expires; (c) *timeout*: every time a packet arrives, check whether a timeout has expired; and (d) *size*: wait until a certain packet size is achieved. These four policies can be combined.

In *blast* flavor, the packets / frames are sent individually as soon as they arrive, to maximize speed. In addition, they are stored in a linked list. Application-level ACK packets are employed, and the original packets are repeatedly sent until the arrival of the corresponding ACK allows its removal.

As far as the *remote* socket is concerned, when a Simplemux packet arrives, it is managed by the *network to tun/tap* module. It extracts the native packets / frames from the multiplexed bundle and delivers them to the local machine via the *local* socket. In *blast* flavor, this module has three more tasks: first, it sends an ACK as soon as a packet arrives; second, it passes the arrived ACKs to the *blast* module so the corresponding packets / frames can be removed from the list; third, it periodically sends heartbeats to the other end.

Finally, when Robust Header Compression (RoHC) is employed, a UDP *feedback* socket is also required to maintain the synchronization between the header compressor / decompressor of the local and the remote machines.

2.2. Software functionalities

As already explained, the developed Simplemux implementation has three *flavors* (*compressed*, *fast* and *blast*), two *tunnel modes* (*tun* and *tap*), three *modes* (*network*, *UDP* and *TCP*), and it can be used with or without RoHC compression. This results in 36 options, in addition to the four multiplexing policies. However, not all the combinations do make sense or have been implemented. Table 1 details the options that are available.

The use of RoHC only makes sense when *tun* tunnelling mode is employed: it can compress IP, UDP and RTP, but it does not work with the Ethernet header.

TCP has only been implemented for the *fast* flavor. It does not make sense in *blast* flavor, as it already employs application-level ACKs. In *compressed* flavor, it cannot be employed because of the variable size of the Simplemux header.

In *blast* flavor, the packet is sent immediately, and no multiplexing policies are employed. In that case, the period defines how often copies are sent.

Table 1
Options of the Simplemux implementation.

	tunneling mode	Mode			RoHC	Multiplexing policies
		Network	UDP	TCP		
Compressed	tun	x	x		x	number, size, timeout, period
	tap	x	x			
Fast	tun	x	x	x	x	number, size, timeout, period
	tap	x	x	x		
Blast	tun	x	x			Always 1 packet
	tap	x	x			

The software can generate log files, and some Perl scripts are also offered for the calculation of throughput, delay, etc., using log traces as an input.

Regarding the usage of the software, it must be invoked from the command prompt, with the classic format in which the user can specify the two interfaces, the IP of the peer, the different options, ports, debug levels, the multiplexing policies and the logging options. The optimization does not need to be symmetrical, i.e., different policies can be specified on each side.

Finally, the repository also includes three Lua scripts that can be added as plug-ins to Wireshark, allowing the dissection of the Simplemux traffic.

3. Illustrative examples

This section illustrates the main functions of the software. As the published repository includes a set of .pcap files, we will refer to them in each case.

3.1. ICMP/IP packets sent in tun tunneling mode, IP mode, with $N = 2$

In this case, a policy has been set that queues IP packets and sends them in pairs, according to the $N = 2$ policy. Fig. 4 presents a Wireshark screenshot dissecting the packets of *simplemux_ip_over_ip_prot_253_n_2.pcap* with the developed Lua plug-ins. IP packet #14 contains two Simplemux separators, each followed by a full ICMP/IP packet. The first separator is three bytes long, because it includes a flag indicating that all packets belong to the same protocol, and a byte expressing the IANA Protocol Number (in this case, it is 4, corresponding to IPv4).

3.2. UDP/IP packets sent in tun tunneling mode, UDP mode, using RoHC compression

This example is illustrated in the Wireshark capture *simplemux_rohc_over_udp_port_55555.pcap*. IP packets are sent from one machine to another via a router. The two routers create a Simplemux tunnel which also implements RoHC to reduce the size of UDP and IP packet headers. In this case, the IANA Protocol Number included in the Simplemux header is 142, which corresponds to RoHC.

3.3. ICMP/IP packets sent in tun tunneling mode, via TCP

This example is illustrated in the Wireshark capture *simplemux_ip_over_tcp_port_55555.pcap*. In this case, the tunneling protocol is TCP and Simplemux *fast* flavor is employed. ICMP requests are carried with Simplemux, inside a TCP packet. TCP ACKs of the same session can also be observed.

3.4. ICMP/IP/Ethernet frames sent in tap tunneling mode, network mode, fast flavor

In this example, a Layer-2 tunnel is created with Simplemux *fast*. It

Fig. 4. Wireshark capture *simplemUX_ip_over_ip_prot_253_n_2.pcap*: dissection of an IP packet carrying two ICMP/IP packets, each of them preceded by a SimplemUX separator.

joins two remote networks, as if the two ends were sharing the same infrastructure. In one end, whole Ethernet frames are captured and released at the other end, as shown in Fig. 5(a). Fig. 5(b) presents the protocol stack in which Ethernet frames are sent in network mode. The Wireshark capture is *simplemUXfast_eth_over_ip_254.pcap*. In the example, ICMP requests have been captured by a *tap* interface, and sent to another machine via the tunnel. SimplemUX is carried over IP and encapsulates an Ethernet frame corresponding to IANA Protocol Number 143.

3.5. GOOSE frames sent in tap tunneling mode, using blast flavor over UDP

In this example, used in [10], IEC 61,850 GOOSE control frames are sent over UDP using SimplemUX *blast* flavor, as shown in *simplemUXblast_carrying_GOOSE_port_55558.pcap*. GOOSE operates at Layer 2 and does not use IP. Several observations can be made: first, every packet has an identifier, which is included in the application-level ACK. The IANA

Protocol Number is 143, which corresponds to Ethernet. In the same trace, application-level ACKs can be observed, which acknowledge previous packets.

4. Impact

As explained in Section 1.2, this software has been employed for answering different research questions. In the case of *traffic optimization* functionality, the trade-off between bandwidth savings and added delays has been explored in different papers already cited [3–5]. The main question is about the kind of traffic that can be optimized: in many cases, small-packet flows correspond to services with tight real-time constraints, e.g., VoIP or online games. The tests carried out with captures of different commercial online games showed that the traffic profile of these services makes it possible to achieve significant bandwidth savings (in some cases >50 %).

The additional delay tolerated by real-time services is very low [20],

Fig. 5. SimplemUX tunnel connecting two networks at Layer 2: a) setup; b) protocol stack.

i.e. in some cases it can be in the order of tens of milliseconds or less. Therefore, they can only be aggregated in network locations where a high number of flows is present, so optimization can occur with minimal delay. The effect on VoIP and Quality of Service was studied in [4], grouping different numbers of flows, and calculating the effect on a subjective quality estimator (ITU's R-Factor). A slightly different methodology was employed with online games, i.e., the addition of different multiplexing periods. It was shown that First Person Shooters tolerate very little delay: in [21], delays between 5 and 15 ms were considered. In contrast, the limits of MMORPG are less strict, so a multiplexing period of 10–20 ms was recommended [5,8].

In addition to the savings in terms of bandwidth, there is an additional benefit which has also been studied: the reduction in packets per second. The modification of the traffic, shifting from profiles with a high rate of small packets to alternative ones in which the number of packets is reduced by means of aggregation, is also beneficial for switching and routing devices. An open research question is whether this traffic profile modification may or may not result in energy savings. As an example, in [9], an anonymized capture from the public Internet was optimized using a size limit of 200 bytes. It resulted in the aggregation of 7908 packets travelling into 395 multiplexed ones.

As far as the *fast delivery grant* functionality is concerned, the next research question has been studied: how to optimally send certain kinds of traffic between remote electrical facilities. A scenario was built within the H2020 FARCROSS project, in which several Phasor Measurement Units sent their reports to a central computer where different grid protection algorithms were run [10]. In this case, the suitability of *blast* flavor for the sending of the event-driven commands generated by the protection algorithms was tested in a realistic scenario including a Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) that simulates an electric grid, and two other commercial devices: a Phasor Measurement Unit that gets the measurements and a Real-Time Automation Controller that runs the protection algorithms.

A trade-off between delay and overhead appears: on the one hand, sending the same packet a number of times until it is acknowledged is beneficial: if the first copy is lost in the network, another one will arrive soon, without the delay incurred by mechanisms like TCP ACK, which imply at least a round-trip time. The periods considered in [10] for the sending of copies of the packets were between 5 and 50 ms, which resulted in different redundancy factors, as a function of the RTT of the network. On the other hand, the same packet will be sent several times, resulting in significant overhead. However, the flows of interest send commands, and do not consume significant bandwidth, so the overhead can be tolerable.

This trade-off is being explored within the Horizon Europe ESTELAR project: different network technologies to connect remote facilities are being explored and compared, including their suitability as backup connectivity options during events such as blackouts.

5. Conclusions

This paper has presented a user-space implementation of Simplemux. It has been used in different research studies and is made available for the scientific community to enable further studies. The software has two main functionalities, namely *traffic saving* and *fast delivery grant*. The first one can provide significant bandwidth savings, along with a reduction in the number of packets per second processed by the network. The second one has the objective of reducing the delivery latency of the packets, at the cost of some redundancy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jose Saldana: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- [1] IANA, Internet assigned numbers authority, protocol numbers, available at <https://www.iana.org/assignments/protocol-numbers/protocol-numbers.xhtml>, accessed Sept 2025.
- [2] Sandlund, K., G. Pelletier, and L.E. Jonsson. "RFC 5795: the RObust header compression (ROHC) framework." (2010). <https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC5795>.
- [3] Saldana J, Fernández-Navajas J, Ruiz-Mas J, Aznar JI, Viruete E, Casadesus L. First person shooters: can a smarter network save bandwidth without annoying the players? IEEE Commun Mag November 2011;49(11):190–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2011.6069728>.
- [4] Saldana J, Fernández-Navajas J, Ruiz-Mas Murillo J, Viruete E, Aznar JI. Evaluating the influence of multiplexing schemes and buffer implementation on perceived VoIP conversation quality. Comput Netw (Elsevier) May 2012;56(7): 1893–919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2012.02.004>.
- [5] Saldana J. On the effectiveness of an optimization method for the traffic of TCP-based multiplayer online games. Multimed Tools Appl Dec. 2016;75:17333–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-015-3001-y>.
- [6] Saldana J, Fernández-Navajas J, Ruiz-Mas J, Wing D, Perumal MAM, Ramalho M, Camarillo G, Pascual F, Lopez DR, Nunez M, Florez D, Castell JA, de Cola T, Beriolli M. Emerging real-time services: optimizing traffic by smart cooperation in the network. IEEE Commun Mag Nov. 2013;51(11):127–36. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2013.6658664>.
- [7] ; Gupta A, Kar S. Analysis of packet aggregation on cloud games. In: 2020 IEEE 17th India Council International Conference (INDICON). IEEE; 2020. p. 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INDICON49873.2020.9342583>.
- [8] Suznjevic M, Saldana J, Matijasevic M, Vuga M. Impact of Simplemux traffic optimisation on MMORPG QoE. In: InISCA/DEGA Workshop on Perceptual Quality of Systems (PQS 2016); 2016. p. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.21437/PQS.2016-4>.
- [9] Saldana J, Forcén I, Fernández-Navajas J, Ruiz-Mas J. Improving network efficiency with Simplemux. In: 2015 IEEE International Conference on Computer and Information Technology; Ubiquitous Computing and Communications; Dependable, Autonomic and Secure Computing; Pervasive Intelligence and Computing. IEEE; 2015. p. 446–53. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIT/IUCC/DASC/PICOM.2015.64>. Oct 26.
- [10] Saldana J, Prada Hurtado AA, Martínez Carrasco E, Galve Y, Torres J. Fast and reliable sending of generic object oriented substation event frames between remote locations over loss-prone networks. Sensors 2023;23(21):8879. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23218879>.
- [11] Krommydas KF, et al. Enhancing the operation of the Hellenic transmission system through wide-area monitoring and control: design, implementation, and evaluation of a phasor measurement unit-based system with advanced algorithms. IEEE Power Energy Mag 2025;23(1):99–112. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPE.2024.3435171>. Jan.-Feb.
- [12] Farinacci, D., Li, T., Hanks, S., Meyer, D., and P. Traina, "Generic routing encapsulation (GRE)," RFC 2784, March 2000, doi: 10.17487/RFC2784.
- [13] Santoso B, Sani A, Husain T, Hendri N. VPN site to site implementation using protocol L2TP and IPsec. 4. Teknokom; 2021. p. 30–6. <https://doi.org/10.31943/teknokom.v4i1.59>.
- [14] Gross J, Ganga I, Sridhar T. Geneve: generic network virtualization encapsulation. RFC 8926; November 2020. <https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC8926>.
- [15] Mirsky, G., Boutros, S., Black, D., & Pallagatti, S. (2025). RFC 9772 Active Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (OAM) for use in generic network virtualization encapsulation (Geneve). 10.17487/RFC9772.
- [16] Ed., Iyengar J, Thomson M. QUIC: a UDP-Based multiplexed and secure transport. Ed., RFC 9000; May 2021. <https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC9000>.
- [17] Budiyo S, Gunawan D. Comparative analysis of VPN protocols at layer 2 focusing on voice over internet protocol. IEEE Access 2023;11:60853–65. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3286032>.
- [18] Akter H, Jahan S, Saha S, Faisal RH, Islam S. Evaluating performances of VPN tunneling protocols based on application service requirements. eds. In: Kaiser MS, Ray K, Bandyopadhyay A, Jacob K, Long KS, editors. Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Trends in Computational and Cognitive Engineering348. Springer; 2022. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-7597-3_36. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems.

- [19] ROHC library, An efficient, free, and opensource header compression library. Available at <https://rohc-lib.org/>, accessed Sept 2025.
- [20] Suznjevic M, Saldana J. Delay limits for real-time services. IETF draft; 2016. June 13, 2016. Available at, <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-suznjevic-tsvwg-delay-limits>. accessed Sept 2025.
- [21] Saldana J, Fernández-Navajas J, Ruiz-Mas Viruete E, Casadesus L. Influence of online games traffic multiplexing and router buffer on subjective quality. In: Proc. CCNC 2012- 4th IEEE International Workshop on Digital Entertainment, Networked Virtual Environments, and Creative Technology (DENVECT); Jan 2012. p. 482–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCNC.2012.6181001>.